

Saint Spyridon, Kardamyli, southern Greece, postbyzantine church

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The church of Saint Spyridon is located in Kardamyli, at the fortified compound of the Mourtzi noi-Troupakis local clan (local landlords called kapetani oi), in the region of messinian Mani, Peloponnese, southern Greece. It is one of the finest example of a single-aisled, barrel-vaulted domed basilica, dated in the 18th century, built of rubble masonry and in the south side, of massive poros blocks. The entrance door and window are framed by sculpted decoration. Parts of sculpture and masonry are of ancient and byzantine origin and dating, indicating re-use of older material in the monument. The impressive bell-tower is decorated by low relief motifs and its structure bear resemblance to western patterns. The church of Saint Spyridon is among the very rare cases of such dominant religious monuments associated with a "clan" and included within their fortification enclosure. It was never purposed to fulfill wide audience worship but only privately, the members of the clan. After the last descendants passed away, the building was left to decay. Some years ago it was restored; but still it only celebrates the patron Saint's day and at some other special occasions (baptisms, weddings).

Date Range: 1700 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Kardamyli, messinian Mani, Messinia, Peloponnese, southern Greece

Region tags: Greece

Kardamyli is a coastal village in messinian Mani, southwestern Messinia, in Peloponnese, southern Greece. It preserves the mountainous prehistoric acropolis, postbyzantine fortified complex of Mourtzi noi-Troupakis clan (now museum) and the traditional architecture of the postbyzantine settlement.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: M. Michailidis - A. Christophidou, Aghios Spyridon at Kardamyli (Western Mani), *Εκκλησίες στην Ελλάδα μετά την Άλωση*, Athens 1982, v. 2, 299-310 (in Greek with English abstract)
- Source 2: *Settlements of Mani*, Athens 2004, 162-172

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.efames.gr/troupakides_gr.html

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Back in medieval times historical circumstances allowed for interaction with roman catholic religious groups (mainly Franks, in lesser extent in that region with Venetians). Compulsory "contact" was implemented by the dominance of the muslim Ottomans after 1460.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Especially with the muslim Ottomans

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There were constant fights between different ethnicities, and consecutively, with different religious groups.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Through the ceremony of Baptism. Nowadays, it is optionally.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: That is for modern era. To a great extent, it was compulsory at medieval times

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Up to nowadays, religious affiliation through Baptism is traditionally assigned at very early years of life.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Through the ceremony of Baptism

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: It was attempted at medieval times

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: There was always a strong connection between Orthodox Church and the (byzantine or modern Greek) State. Nowadays, political support to Church is still active but limited.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– I don't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Back in medieval times that must have been not an unusual phenomenon

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Initially the church was purposed for limited number of people, just for the members of the clan, perhaps some guards also. Today, it is only celebrating at the Feast day of the patron saint or in special occasions of ceremonies (baptisms, weddings)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: This is the local priest

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– I don't know

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– I don't know

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– I don't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– I don't know

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– I don't know

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– I don't know

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– I don't know

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– I don't know

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: conception of Paradise

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No

- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - No

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: salvation from sins-deliverance of sooul

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– I don't know

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– I don't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes

↳ Cooperation:
– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– No

↳ Strength (physical):
– I don't know

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: optionally

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: optionally

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: optionally

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: optionally

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saint Spyridon, Kardamyli, southern Greece, postbyzantine church, Christophidou, Athina . "The Fortified Complexes of the Kapetanies. The Example of the Troupakis - Moutrzinis Clan". In *Settlements of Mani, 2004:162-72*. Athens, 2004.

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